

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13358896

Psychosocial Factors as Determinants of Academic Engagement among Senior Secondary School Students in the Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria

¹Fehintola, Joseph Olusola PhD & ²Olaosebikan, Olusola Isaac PhD

¹Department of Counselling & Human Development Studies,
University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

Telephone Number: 08162023919/08056240315

E-Mail: jof677@yahoo.com/joseph.fehintola@gmail.com/fehintola.j@dlc.ui.edu.ng

²Counselling and Human Development Centre,
University of Medical Sciences, Ondo, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study, therefore, investigated psychosocial factors as determinants of academic engagement among senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis with a view to examining academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer influence as determinants of academic engagement among the selected students. The study employed descriptive survey design of correlational type. The study sample included 255 senior secondary school male and female students in SS 1 and SS 2 classes randomly selected among secondary school students in the Ibadan metropolis. 50% of the participants were females and 46.9% were males while 3.1% did not indicate their gender. The participants' mean age was 15.84 with the standard deviation of 1.78. Four-Dimensional Scale of Academic Engagement (4DSAE) ($\alpha = 0.82$), Academic Motivation Scale- High School Version (AMS-HSV) ($\alpha = 0.84$), Academic Self-concept Questionnaire (ASCQ) ($\alpha = 0.83$) and Perceived Peer Pressure Scale (PPPS) ($\alpha = 0.94$) were used for collecting the data. Three research questions were raised and answered and data were analysed using Correlation and Regression Analysis. The findings revealed that academic motivation ($r = 0.617$, $p < 0.05$), academic self-concept ($r = 0.273$, $p < 0.05$) and peer pressure ($r = -0.372$, $p < 0.05$) had significant relationship with academic engagement. However, peer pressure had significant but negative relationship with academic engagement. It was evident that academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer pressure put together had significant relationship with academic performance and significantly predicted it with $F = 55.249$, $R = 0.630$, $R^2 = 0.387$, $p < 0.05$. It was also revealed that academic motivation ($\beta = 0.555$, $t = 8.418$, $p < 0.05$) made the most significant positive contribution to the total variation in the academic engagement, academic self-concept ($\beta = 0.009$, $t = 0.148$, $p > 0.05$) made no significant contribution while peer pressure ($\beta = -0.140$, $t = -2.267$, $p > 0.05$) made significant but negative contribution. Only academic motivation and peer pressure are significant relative predictors of academic engagement in the study. Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that academic motivation and peer pressure are significant psychosocial determinants of academic engagement of senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis. It was therefore recommended that all stakeholders should make provision for and implement counselling services and programmes in schools to address student academic engagement using motivation, self-concept and peer pressure.

Keywords: Psychosocial factors, Academic motivation, Academic self-concept, Peer influence, Ibadan metropolis

INTRODUCTION

Academic Engagement described as a malleable, developing, and multidimensional construct that consists of three broad dimensions such as behavioural, cognitive, and emotional. These dimensions are not isolated but interrelate with each other. The behavioural dimension is found to be a crucial factor in mediating the dropout process. The first way involves positive conduct, such as adhering to the norms of the classroom, following the rules, and refraining from engaging in disruptive behaviours. The second way pertains to participation in learning and academic-related tasks, and involves behaviours such as discussion contribution, asking questions, paying attention, concentrating, exhibiting persistence, and putting forth effort. The third dimension is the involvement in activities related to school that include, school governance and sports. Therefore, behavioural engagement is a directly observable dimension of engagement, and the salient indicators of this dimension include truancy, preparation for school, attendance, participation in curricular and extracurricular tasks, and discipline referrals.

There are many researchers (Bond, Butler, Thomas, Carlin, Glower, & Bowes, 2007) that have worked on this construct – academic engagement. Some identified psychosocial factors that are capable of determining students' academic engagement are academic self-concept, emotional intelligence, academic motivation, personal well-being, peer influence, self-efficacy and parental involvement, among others. However, this study only focuses its attention on academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer influence as psychosocial factors that are determinants of academic engagement among senior secondary school students in the Ibadan metropolis.

Academic motivation refers to the cause of behaviours that are in some way related to academic functioning and success, such as how much effort students put forth, how effectively they regulate their work, which endeavors they choose to pursue, and how persistent they are when faced with obstacles. Moreover, academic motivation is an essential part of learning and achievement. It is one of the most important factors that lead one to one's goals. This drive is known as motivation. Motivation is widely acknowledged to enhance performance and efficiency of the students as well as the men for learning. Even motivation modifies the learning goal and achievement of students (Hartney, 2024). It refers to reasons that underlie the behavior that is characterised by willingness and choice. Academic motivation can develop confidence in one's ability along with an increased value of education and desire to learn. Motivation is closely related to learning, achieving a desired object, nurturing a hobby, attaining a goal. It may be intrinsic as well as extrinsic. Academic motivation is perceived as the source of a person's motivation may be intrinsic, derived from internal processes, and/or extrinsic, the result of external forces. Likewise, individuals can be impelled to act by conscious and non-conscious motives. Academic motivation refers to the cause of behaviours that are in some way related to academic functioning and success. Similarly, academic motivation is a student's desire (as reflected in approach, persistence, and level of interest) regarding academic subjects when the student's competence is judged against a standard of performance or excellence (Bakker, Vergel, & Kuntze, 2015; Dotterer & Lowe, 2011; Wigfield & Eccles, 2002).

Furthermore, academic self-concept can be defined as one's academic self-perceptions or one's perception of one's general ability in school. Academic self-concept relates to how well an individual feels they can learn. It can vary across academic disciplines and can be affected by past academic performance. Students with high levels of academic self-concept are those students that feel they can do well in their school work. According to Olalekan (2016), it is generally observed that peer group has a lot of influence on students. This is seen from the role played by the peer group in the life and learning of a child, evidence abound that students feel more comfortable and relaxed among fellow students. A child who is brilliant and surrounded by dull friends would lose interest in learning. On the other hand, a peer group which is prone to study would have positive effect on a dull member towards learning and stimulate his/her interest on learning. Katz in Olalekan (2016) wrote that the nature of a peer group determines the impact on the motivation of and achievements of its member. He further suggested that one group may have a negative impact on its members while the other may have positive impact on its members as well.

Peer pressure is defined as when people of the same age (peer group) encourage or implore one to do something or to keep from doing something else, whether an individual wants to do it or not (Ryan, 2002; Boundless Psychology, 2015). According to Burns and Darling (2002), the more subtle form of peer pressure is known as peer influence which involves changing ones' behaviour to meet the perceived expectations of others. It is the influence and demands that come from association, connection or attachment of an adolescent to a group of other adolescents. The group may be formal or informal but members exhibit similar attitudes, behaviours, likes and dislikes. All children experience peer pressure and give in to it at one time or another. Peer pressure is part of almost all children's lives (Kessler, 2012). Peer pressure is the process by which members of the same social group influence other members to do things that they may be resistant to, or might not otherwise choose to do. Peers are people who are part of the same social group, so the term "peer pressure" refers to the influence that peers can have on each other. Usually, the term peer pressure is used when people are talking about behaviours that are not considered socially acceptable or desirable, such as experimentation with alcohol or drugs. Though peer pressure is not usually used to describe socially desirable behaviors, such as exercising or studying, peer pressure can have positive effects in some cases.

This study will attempt to investigate the foregoing variables by focusing attention on how they impact academic engagement of senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis. This will allow for a unique study that contributes to what is known about psychosocial factors that determine student academic engagement.

Statement of the Problem

There are several factors that have tendencies to hamper the academic engagement of senior secondary school students. Extant studies have tried to investigate some of these factors and how they influence student academic engagement.

Academic engagement has become one of the desired outcomes of school in recent years because of its strong connection to student academic performance. In particular, previous research had demonstrated decisive links between student engagement in learning and such outcomes as school dropout, substance use, mental health, and academic outcomes. Students engaged in learning were found to be more successful academically, as well as less likely to drop out of school. They were found to be intrinsically motivated to invest in learning, attend classes, and participate in study activities. As student engagement is widely presumed to be flexible, it is relevant to both explore the predictors of school engagement and outline factors that can be stimulated in order to positively influence it. Therefore, in light of the described positive consequences of student academic engagement, the current study aims at contributing to the growing body of research by interrogating the psychosocial factors as determinants of academic engagement among senior secondary school students in the Ibadan metropolis, Oyo State.

Purpose of the Study

The study investigated psychosocial factors - Academic motivation, Academic self-concept and Peer influence- as determinants of academic engagement among senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis and the specific objectives are to:

- a. investigate the correlation between Academic motivation, Academic self-concept and Peer influence and Academic engagement among senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis
- b. to examine the composite contribution of psychosocial factors on Academic engagement among senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis;
- a. examine the relative contributions of Academic motivation, Academic self-concept and Peer influence to the observable changes in the Academic engagement of senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised and answered in the study.

Research Question One: What is the pattern of relationship between selected psychosocial factors and academic engagement of senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis?

Research Question Two: What is the joint contribution of Academic motivation, Academic self-concept and Peer influence to the observable changes in the academic engagement of senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis?

Research Question Three: What are the relative contributions of Academic motivation, Academic self-concept and Peer influence to the observable changes in the Academic engagement of senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design for this study is descriptive research design of correlational type. This design was used because it allows the researcher to investigate the relationship between independent and dependent variables and to determine the predictive effects of the independent variables on the dependent variable without manipulating any variable.

Population

The population for this study consisted of all public senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample was two hundred (255) senior secondary school students drawn from among senior secondary schools in the Ibadan metropolis. Simple random sampling technique was used to select the sample from the population.

Instrumentation

Four instruments were used to collect data in this study. The section A of the questionnaire requires the participants to supply their demographic information such as age, gender, class, arm of the class (i.e., science, commercial or arts), and religious affiliation. The remaining sections B, C, D and E present the four instruments as discussed below:

Section B: Four-Dimensional Scale of Academic Engagement (4DSAE)

The SESA-4DS was developed by VeIga (2016) and presented as a second version of the one developed in 2013. The SESA-4DS measures four dimensions/components of student academic engagement in school instead of the three measured by the previous scales. The four dimensions include behavioural engagement, affective/emotional engagement, cognitive engagement and agency engagement. The SESA-4DS contains 20 items to which the participants are required respond using 6-point Likert-type response format range from 'Total Disagreement' =1, 'Disagreement' =2, 'More Disagreement than Agreement' =3, 'More Agreement than Disagreement' =4, 'Agreement' =5, and 'Total agreement' =6.

The psychometric properties of the SESA-4DS, by the developer is ($\alpha =0.82$) it revealed that the SESA-4DS is highly reliable. This instrument was revalidated by the researchers and it yielded reliability coefficient ($\alpha =0.76$) using Cronbach alpha.

Section C: Academic Motivation Scale- High School Version (AMS-HSV)

Academic Motivation Scale – High School Version (AMSHSV) was developed by Vallerand, Pelletier, Blais, Brière, Senècal, and Vallières (1992, 1993). AMSHSV contains 28 items which are grouped into 7 subscales and it was used to measure academic engagement of the participants. The subscales measure three intrinsic motivation forms- accomplishment, knowledge and stimulation; three extrinsic motivation forms- external, identified and interjected, and lastly amotivation. Each of the seven subscales contains 4 items. This means that 12 items assess the intrinsic type and 12 another assess extrinsic type, while only 4 items assess amotivation type. The psychometric properties of AMSHSV indicated that the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of the seven subscales range from .71 to .84, thereby confirming that the scale is highly reliable.

Section D: Academic Self-concept Questionnaire (ASCQ)

Academic Self-concept Questionnaire (ASCQ) was adapted from Self-Description Questionnaire-II developed by Marsh (1992). It was adapted by Areepattamannil (2011) to Indian immigration and Indian adolescents' academic self-concept. ASCQ contains 30 items which grouped into three subscales. Each

subscale contains 10 items. The subscales include mathematics self-concept, verbal self-concept and general school self-concept. The respondents were required to respond to the items using 6-point Likert scale response format: 1= False, 2= Mostly false, 3= More False Than True, 4= More True Than False, 5= Mostly True, and 6= True. The psychometric properties reported for ASCQ revealed that the Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficients for the entire items ranged between 0.83 and .91 and for the subscales, mathematics self-concept was 0.91, verbal self-concept was 0.83 while general school self-concept was 0.83. These all showed that ASCQ is reliable.

Section E: Perceived Peer Pressure Scale (PPPS)

PPPS was developed by Palani and Mani (2016) to measure the perceived peer pressure of senior secondary school students. The scale contains 30 items divided into 3 subscales- yielding to peer pressure, resistance to peer pressure and peers encouragement. The PPPS items require the participants to respond using five point Likert-type response format such as 'Strongly Agree' = 5, 'Agree' = 4, 'Undecided' = 3, 'Disagree' = 2 and 'Strongly Disagree' = 1. Thus, high scores on the scale indicate higher level of exposure to peer pressure while low scores indicate lower level of exposure to peer pressure as perceived by the participants. The reliability and validity analysis yielded Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of 0.942 and 0.971 respectively.

Procedure of Administration

To administer the copies of the questionnaire on the participants, the researchers moved round the public secondary schools selected for the study, having secured permission from the school authorities. The researchers also engaged the assistance of teachers in collecting the data in those schools.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Inferential statistical tools include Pearson's Product Moment correlation analysis to determine the pattern of the relationship and Multiple Regression analysis to determine the predictive effects of the dependent variables on the dependent variable.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the joint contribution of academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer pressure to the observable changes in the academic engagement of senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis?*

Table 4.1.1: Summary of Correlation between Independent Variables (Academic Motivation, Academic Self-concept and Peer Pressure) and Academic Engagement

	1	2	3	4
Academic Engagement	1.000			
Academic Motivation	.617**	1.000		
Academic Self-concept	.273**	.415**	1.000	
Peer Pressure	-.372**	-.414**	-.243	1.000
Mean	76.7500	105.4700	114.1500	80.8418
Standard Deviation	11.14169	22.02619	22.37185	15.83668

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table1 shows the variables' mean, Standard Deviation, and zero-order correlation. It was observed that there was significant relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable (academic engagement). There was significant relationship between academic motivation ($r = 0.617, p < 0.05$), academic self-concept ($r = 0.273, p < 0.05$) and peer pressure ($r = -0.372, p < 0.05$) on academic engagement of secondary school students.

Research Question Two: *What is the joint contribution of Academic motivation, Academic self-concept and Peer influence to the observable changes in the academic engagement of senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis?*

Table 2: The Joint Contribution of Academic Motivation, Academic Self-concept and Peer Pressure to Academic Engagement

R = 0.630, R ² = 0.397, Adjusted R ² = 0.387, Std. Error of the Estimation = 8.72090					
Analysis of Variance					
Sources of Variation	Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig
Regression	9604.358	3	3201.453	55.249	0.000
Residual	14602.392	252	57.946		
Total	24206.750	255			

Table 2 above shows that the joint effect of the independent variables (academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer pressure) on academic engagement of the study participants was significant. The multiple regression yielded a coefficient of F= 55.249, R of 0.630 and adjusted R² of 0.387 which accounted for about 38.7% of the total variation in the participants’ academic engagement. This result implies that academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer pressure when pulled together significantly determined academic engagement of the study participants. Therefore, academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer pressure are significant joint predictors of academic engagement of the study participants.

Research Question 3: What are the relative contributions of Academic motivation, Academic self-concept and peer pressure to the observable changes in the Academic engagement of senior secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis?

Table 3: Multiple Regression Analysis Result of Relative Contributions of the Independent Variables to the Prediction of Academic Engagement of the Study Participants

Model	Un-standardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	B		
(Constant)	54.606	6.291		8.680	.000
Academic Motivation	.281	.033	.555	8.418	.000
Academic Self-concept	.005	.031	.009	.148	.883
Peer Pressure	-.099	.043	-.140	-2.267	.024

According Table 3 above, academic motivation contributed ($\beta = 0.555$, $t = 8.418$, $p < 0.05$), academic self-concept contributed ($\beta = 0.009$, $t = 0.148$, $p > 0.05$) while peer pressure contributed ($\beta = -0.140$, $t = -2.267$, $p > 0.05$) to the total variation in the academic engagement of the study participants. This result proves that only academic motivation made the most significantly positive contribution to the prediction of academic engagement in the study. The contribution of academic self-concept was low and insignificant, while that of peer pressure was significant but negative. Therefore, while academic motivation was a significant positive predictor of the participants’ academic engagement, peer pressure was a significant negative predictor indicating that peer pressure prevents students to do the needful on students’ academic pursuit. On the contrary, academic self-concept was not a significant predictor of academic engagement in this study but its contribution is not substantial.

DISCUSSION

Research Question One

The result of research question one showed that three independent variables were significantly correlated with academic engagement. This is an indication that all the three variables are significantly germane to academic engagement an indication that they are potent determinants of academic engagement. This study has found that though academic self-concept was a significant correlate of the participants’ academic engagement. This finding is in consonance with the study of Hamed, Jayervand and Hooman (2023) which also reported a positive and significant correlation between academic self-concept and academic

engagement. Academic motivation was a significant correlate of academic engagement among participants studied this result did corroborate the findings of Zhang, Guan, Ahmed, Jobe and Ahmed (2022) and Ebadolahi, Barzegar and Kazemi (2020) who found that academic motivation was a positive and significant correlate, and a significant predictor of academic engagement of secondary school students whether gifted or not. Peer pressure in the same vein also served as a significant correlates among participants, This finding therefore supports the conclusion of Zhang, Guan, Ahmed, Jobe and Ahmed (2022) that academic peer pressure could impact on the levels of academic engagement, performance in academic activities and assignments either positively or negatively.

On research question two the results showed that the joint effect of the independent variables (academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer pressure) on academic engagement of the study participants was significant. This is an indication that, academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer pressure are significant joint predictors of academic engagement of the participants in the study. This means that for any attempt to enhance academic engagement of students, academic motivation, and academic self-concept and peer pressure should be explored.

This result corroborates the findings of Guthrie and Wigfield's (2000) model of reading engagement. According to the model, for students to be actively engaged in reading that results to achievement in knowledge and practices, there must be motivation, social interactions, conceptual knowledge and strategy use. In order to achieve this, the model identified factors that must interact to create the synergy such as is the case with this result. In the same vein, this finding also supports the postulation of the Venn diagram model of student engagement that student engagement is an output of two important input variables, motivation and active learning (Ganeshinis, 2011). According to the model, engaged students must demonstrate motivational characteristics such as high expectations, interest and value for their education and academic tasks, and actively participate in them regardless of whether they are difficult or simple. Thus, Venn diagram model of student engagement provides the basis for evaluating the characteristics of engaged learners in this study. This study has confirmed that academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer pressure are important characteristics of such learners.

The result of third research question on relative contributions independent variables on academic engagement proved that only academic motivation made the most significantly positive contribution to the prediction of academic engagement in the study. The contribution of academic self-concept was low and insignificant, while that of peer pressure was significant but negative. Therefore, the finding that academic motivation was a significant positive predictor of academic engagement in this study corroborates (Siddique, Jabeen and Akhtar, 2023) who found that academic motivation was both a significant correlate and potent predictor of academic engagement of their study participants. This finding is partly in line with the findings of Atik and Celik (2021) who also found academic motivation to be a significant but negative predictor of academic engagement. Similarly, the findings of Mutsiya, Dinga and Kinai (2019) on Kenyan secondary school students' academic motivation and perceptions of teacher support and their predictive effects on academic engagement were supported by this study. The researchers found that though both academic motivation and student perceptions of teacher support were positively and significantly correlated with academic engagement, they found academic motivation to be the most significant predictor of academic engagement.

The findings of Akpan and Umobong (2013) among senior secondary school students in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria were also buttressed by this study. Akpan and Umobong (2013) found that achievement motivation levels had significant predictive effects on the academic engagement of their study participants. They found significant differences in the academic engagement of the participants who were highly, moderately and lowly motivated. This proves that the highly motivated students were the most significantly engaged academically compared to the remaining motivation levels. The findings of Babatunde and Olanrewaju (2014) among the Nigerian subjects were also supported. These findings are unique because the researchers found that the association between academic motivation and academic engagement was reciprocal, and therefore concluded that highly motivated students were highly engaged academically, while highly engaged students were also found to be highly motivated academically.

Furthermore, this study also found that peer pressure was a significant negative predictor of academic engagement of participants. This implies that the negative peer relationships kept by the study participants or their high exposure to peer pressure was responsible for their reduced academic engagement in this study. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Kharb and Chahal (2023) that confirmed that peer influence played an important role in the way the student behaviour was shaped, especially in relation to social norms and the quest for acceptance in their peer groups.

CONCLUSION

This study has been conducted to examine psychosocial factors (i.e., academic motivation, academic self-concept and peer pressure) as determinants of academic engagement among secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis. The findings of this study have proved that academic motivation and academic self-concept have significant positive relationship with academic engagement but only academic motivation significantly predicts it. The findings also affirmed that peer pressure has a negative significant relationship with academic engagement and significantly predicts it. This study therefore concluded that academic motivation and peer pressure are significant determinants of academic performance of secondary school students in Ibadan metropolis.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusion of this study, the researcher therefore recommends the following:

- i. Government should make provision for and implement counselling services and programmes in schools. This will address student psycho-social variables such motivation, self-concept, self-esteem, peer influence, etc.
- ii. Parents and guardians should make educational materials for their wards and cooperate with their teachers to help students' motivation in school and make workable action plans. This will help to assume responsibility for their own learning.
- iii. Government at various levels, parents, teachers, school counsellors and other stakeholders should make concerted effort to raise standard of education by placing priority on quality education and making necessary provisions for attaining such standard. These include educational reform, training, hiring and reinforcing qualified teaching staff, building of libraries with internet facilities.
- iv. To mitigate the negative effects of peer pressure, there is the need for students to be equipped with resistance skills, positive peer relationships and targeted interventions. Also, educators, parents and policymakers must be aware of this impact and involved so that they can help students navigate peer relationships effectively and promote positive academic outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Akpan, I. D. and Umobong, M. E. (2013). Analysis of achievement motivation and academic engagement of students in the Nigerian classroom. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies* 2.3.
- Areepattamannil, S. 2011. Academic self-concept, academic motivation, academic engagement, and academic achievement: a mixed methods study of Indian adolescents in Canada and India. Dissertation. Education. Queen's University.
- Atik, S. and Çelik, O. T. (2021). Analysis of the relationships between academic motivation, engagement, burnout and academic achievement with structural equation modelling. *International Journal of Contemporary Educational Research* 8.2.
- Babatunde, M. M. and Olanrewaju, M. K. (2014). Predictive influence of students' academic engagement and academic self-concept on achievement motivation among post graduate students in University of Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 3.5.
- Bakker, A. B., Vergel, A. I. S. and Kuntze, J. (2015). Student engagement and performance: A weekly diary study on the role of openness. *Motivation and Emotion*, 39.

- Bond, L., Butler, H., Thomas, L., Carlin, J., Glower, S., Bowes, G., & Patton, G. (2007). Social and school connectedness in early secondary school as predictors of late teenage substance use, mental health, and academic outcomes. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 40.
- Burns, A. and Darling, N. (2002). Peer pressure is not peer influence. *The Education Digest* 68: 4-6.
- Dotterer, A. M. and Lowe, K. (2011). Classroom context, school engagement, and academic achievement in early adolescence. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 40.
- Ebadolahi, M., Barzegar, M. and Kazemi, S. (2020). Compilation of the causal model of the effect of school enrollment on the academic engagement of students with the mediating role of academic self-concept. *Psychological Methods and Models* 11.39.
- Ganeshini, S. K. (2011). Strengthening student engagement in the classroom. Project. Science Communication. Science. National University of Singapore.
- Hamed, Z., Jayervand, H. and Hooman F. (2023). Association of academic engagement with academic self-concept and academic support in gifted students: the mediating role of achievement motivation. *Int. J. School. Health*. 10.3.
- Hartley, E. (2024). What to Know About Peer Pressure: It's not as simple as just saying no. <https://www.verywellmind.com/what-is-peer-pressure-22246>
- Kessler, C. (2012). Approaches to school counseling services and peer's education. Dar es Salaam, Unpublished report.
- Kharb, L. and Chahal, D. (2023). Unravelling the influence of peers- assessing the impact on student behaviour and academic performance in boarding schools of India. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science* 5.7.
- Mutisya, E. N., Dinga, J. N. and Kinai, T. K. (2019). Students' perceptions of teacher support and academic motivation as predictors of academic engagement. *International Journal of Applied Psychology* 9.5.
- Olalekan, A. B. (2016). Influence of peer group relationship on the academic performance of students in secondary schools: A case study of selected secondary schools in Atiba Local Government Area of Oyo State. *Global Journal of Human-Social Science*, 16, 4
- Palani, P. and Mani, S. (2016). Exploratory factor analysis: Development of perceived peer pressure scale. *International Journal of Information Science and Computing* 3.1.
- Ryan M. A. and Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development and well-being. *American Psychologist* 55: 68-78.
- Siddique, T. K. Jabeen, M. A. and Akhtar, P. K. (2023). Peer pressure and peer influence in children and adolescence. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology* 10.3
- Vallerand, R.J., Pelletier, L.G., Blais, M.R., Brière, N. M., Senècal, C. and Vallières, E. F. 1992. The academic motivation scale: A measure of intrinsic, extrinsic, and amotivation in education. *Educational and Psychological Measurement* 52.4.
- Velga, F. H. 2016. Assessing student engagement in school: Development and validation of a four-dimensional. *Procedia- Social and Behavioural sciences*. 217: 813-819. Retrieved Nov. 21, 2017, from [http://repositorio.ul.pt/bitstream/10451/22741/1/Student Engagement in School Devel Valida tion Four-dimensional Scale](http://repositorio.ul.pt/bitstream/10451/22741/1/Student%20Engagement%20in%20School%20Devel%20Validation%20Four-dimensional%20Scale).
- Wigfield, A. (2000). Expectancy-value theory of motivation. *Contemporary Educational Psychology* 25:68-81.
- Wigfield, A. and Eccles, J. S. (2002). *Development of achievement motivation*. San Diego: Academic Press.
- Zhang. Y., Guan, X., Ahmed, M. Z., Jobe, M. C. and Ahmed O. (2022). The association between university students' achievement goal orientation and academic engagement: examining the mediating role of perceived school climate and academic self-efficacy. *Sustainability*14.10: 6304.